

PROBLEMS OF REPERTOIRE FORMATION OF FOLKLORE ENSEMBLES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10682906>

Abstract: this article discusses the formation of repertoires of folklore ethnographic ensembles and the improvement of artistic and creative performance of the repertoire.

Key words: folklore, ethnography, repertoire, performance skills, artistic creativity.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: Folk oral creativity needs protection and protection. The fact that such a unique and great art has become a mere example of a cultural monument, is being forgotten in many places, and needs protection and protection is a bitter reality of our time. I believe that you, as true devotees of this beautiful and unique art, are most worried about you.

For centuries, folklore has been a means of education and a means of encouraging the people to goodness, and for centuries it has served to elevate the spiritual world of the people.

Proper formation of the repertoire of the amateur team is one of the main tasks for the leader. The correct choice of the repertoire has a direct impact on the progress of the creative process in the team, the increase in the activity of the participants and, ultimately, the overall development of the team. Although the repertoire of amateur teams differs in terms of genre and form from that of professional teams, there are some things they have in common. Experts emphasize the need to pay attention to the following when forming the team's repertoire:

1. Selection of ideologically oriented, artistically mature works.
2. Covering a variety of genres. Gradually increasing complexity of the repertoire.
3. Taking into account the participants' capabilities, abilities, as well as their interests and desires.
4. Extensive use of works related to the area where the team operates, the production or agricultural sector there, as well as the nature of the place.
5. Inclusion of examples of folk art, as well as works of local authors in the repertoire.

The creative process carried out in any team must reach a certain point and be brought to the attention of listeners or viewers. Therefore, in the early period of formation of the team's repertoire, it is necessary to determine in what way the selected works can be used. The more colorful works are in the team's repertoire, the easier it is to organize shows on different topics. The creative talent of folklore-ethnographic community leaders in this field is of great practical importance in the preservation and development of folk art. The success of the practical work carried out in the creative team is largely due to its deep sense of the value of artistic words, musicality, the ability to choose and promote the best examples of folk songs, as well as the Uzbek folk song in the development of the individual. depends on how deeply he understands the art of singing and dancing.

Its preservation and application in the process of education has been recognized as the

ethnogenesis of folk pedagogy and has had a positive effect on the education of the nation. Repertoires of folklore-ethnographic works have their place in educating young people as mature people. The creative talent of the leaders of folklore-ethnographic ensembles in this field is of great practical importance in the preservation and development of folk art. The success of the practical work carried out in the creative team largely depends on its deep sense of the value of artistic words, musicality, the ability to choose and promote the best examples of folk songs, as well as the development of a person, how deeply he understands the beauty of Uzbek folk singing and dancing. The best folk songs can be recorded by the performers involved in the ensemble.

In addition, young performers who perform songs learned from the representatives of the older generation in a certain area, or relatives and acquaintances who know such songs, can be involved in the ensemble to perform these songs. Traditional songs can also be recorded from popular bands or singers. Texts collected during folklore expeditions are an important resource for enriching the repertoire of the ensemble with new folk songs. Because the skill, experience and creative skills of the participants of the team in the expeditions in performing songs will increase to a certain extent in the process of direct creative communication with folk hafis and bakhshis.

Texts collected from folklore expeditions are an important resource for enriching the team's repertoire with new folk songs. Team participants in these expeditions can improve their experience and creative skills in performing their songs, and gain specific performance experience in the process of direct creative communication with folk hafis and bakhshis. Therefore, the repertoire is a mirror that determines the ideological and artistic level of the folklore community and its professional creative maturity. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the artistic level and ideological content of folklore works included in the repertoire. In addition, it is necessary to pay great attention to the choice of songs.

Let's dwell on the main principles of repertoire formation: the ideological and artistic authority of the repertoire, its educational potential in the creative community is especially important. It should not be overlooked that the repertoire educates not only the performers who are part of the team, but also the audience, who enjoy their art, and the young people.

In particular, it is necessary to observe that the repertoire consists of various genres of Uzbek folklore. It is desirable to include in the repertoire dance works close to the folk language, especially examples of ritual folklore. Also, the effective use of the most optimal aspects of various performance methods, their generalization, increases the creative potential of the team.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the artistic aspect and ideological content of the folklore work included in the repertoire, as well as to the choice of songs. The following: the artistic-artistic reputation of the repertoire, its educational potential in the creative community; the skill of performers and the audience enjoying their art are the main principles of repertoire formation. Effective use of the most optimal methods of performance, their generalization increases the creative potential of the team. It is worth saying that in the experience of amateur ensembles, the tradition of relying on songs performed in the same style, as well as combining the methods of performing songs from different regions, is noticeable. In our opinion, this method seems more promising in the development of traditional folklore.

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